

Complete biodiverse lignocellulosic biomass fractionation process using the green solvent γ -valerolactone – Supporting Information

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1. Lignin and Hemicellulose extraction process optimization

To calculate the yield of lignin extractions, the overall lignin content in all biomasses had to be determined through CASA UV/Vis spectroscopy. Figure 1 shows the different UV/Vis spectra for the lignin content determination.

Figure 1: UV/Vis spectra of CASA lignin content determination for all used biomass sources, coded by color. Spectra were recorded from 200 to 400 nm. Absorbances at 283 nm were used calculations. For every biomass source, five spectra were measured to determine a mean value and standard deviation.

For the purpose of finding suitable pretreatment and extraction methods for lignin extraction from biomass with GVL, experiments were done with spruce sawdust as biomass source. For the first experiments, extraction methods from different studies were tested¹⁻⁷. Here, the methods derived from Cheng et al⁸ and Gioia et al⁹ proved to be most effective in terms of lignin yield. When talking about lignin yield in this publication, it is always related to the mass of extracted lignin compared to the determined lignin content in the respective biomass.

The most effective method involved putting a set amount of biomass in a 250 mL round flask, including a GVL/water mixture and sulfuric acid. The extraction mixture was first stirred at 100 °C for 1.5 h to receive black liquor. Lignin could be precipitated by the addition of water. Untreated spruce sawdust was subjected to extraction, resulting in a yield of 14.4 %. The water content, which was measured via gravimetry before and after drying at 100 °C for 72 h, was determined to be 51 %. After using dried spruce sawdust as biomass, the yield increased to almost double, 27.5 %, as expected. An increase in extraction time to 2h plus an additional 20 to 30 min of preheating time until the right temperature was reached, and extraction temperature to 120 °C led to yields of up to 42.9 %. In the work of Cheng et al [45], 120 °C and 1.5 h led to the highest yields, but they did not use a reflux cooler, but instead an autoclave under reaction pressure. The increase in temperature and reaction time makes up for this in this thesis, though even higher temperatures >120 °C and reaction times >2 h led to bigger impurities. These come from decomposition of GVL or decomposition of polysaccharide chains. The other reaction parameters were also optimized, which is explained later. Second step and third step extractions were performed, looking to isolate as much lignin as possible. The solid residue of an extraction was dried and used again in fresh solvent. After receiving 42.9 % lignin in a first step, 33.1 % was yielded in a second step and 3.4 % in a third step. Overall, around 80.4 % of lignin could be extracted, even more considering possible losses in filtering and drying post-treatments. Hydrochloric acid was tested instead of sulfuric acid, which led to a yield of 21.4 %. Also, for HCl, the black liquor did not precipitate lignin upon the addition of water. Additional HCl had to be added towards a pH value of 5, where precipitation started again. Sulfuric acid was the more efficient acid component. For better swelling of the biomass cell walls, ultrasonic pretreatment was suggested. With an ultrasonic pretreatment for 30 min at 60 °C and subsequent extraction, a comparably low lignin yield of 26.7 % was achieved. A possible explanation was suggested: Due to ultrasonic treatment, the cells walls swell with solvent. Due to the presence of sulfuric acid, the lignin might already degrade and re-condensate into complex structures involving C-C bonds. These structures are then harder to cleave, leading to a lower yield. To confirm this thesis, ultrasonic pretreatment was done without the addition of the acid component in the mixture. Before the subsequent extraction, the acid component was added. This led to yields of 57.4 % for first step, 28.2 % for second step, and 12.1 % for third step extractions. Compared to the 80.4 % yield without ultrasonic pretreatment, now an overall yield of 97,4 % was achieved. The residual biomass could be considered almost lignin free. Another experiment was done: Four subsequent extractions were performed with the same biomass, each one over 30 min of extraction time, to see if this added up to the same total yield than doing a normal extraction over 2 h of extraction time. An overall yield of only 8.5 % was achieved. Reaction times of 30 min were too short to yield a substantial amount of lignin. The optimal pretreatment method was summarized to be ultrasonic pretreatment without acid addition, 120 °C, 2h plus 20 to 30 min of preheating, three-step extraction, and sulfuric acid as acid component. A deep eutectic solvent of choline chloride and levulinic acid was also used in combination with GVL as a solvent mixture. This yielded 44.2 % lignin after a first extraction step, which is comparable to only GVL/water as solvent, but more complex in terms of preparation and chemicals used. The ability of the solvent to load dissolved lignin was also investigated. After a first extraction step with optimal pretreatment methods found, the residual biomass was filtrated, and new biomass was added to the mixture. The overall yield referring to double the amount of biomass was 25.9 %. The same experiment was performed by adding fresh amounts of sulfuric acid to the mixture with fresh biomass. Here, the yield increased to 49.9 %. The ability of GVL to load dissolved lignin is higher, but the presence of acidic conditions was the deciding factor if extraction continues. As seen in the next paragraph, adding a larger acid concentration also increased the impurities in the extracted lignin samples. An addition of sulfuric acid after some time into the extraction process might help with increasing the yield without compromising the purity for one single extraction step. Additionally, some extreme conditions, such as high

temperature or high extraction times were tested. Extraction times of 24 h up to 3 d led to very increased yields of 95 to 150 %. The degradation of polysaccharide chains took place and many complex lignin structures formed, which were all extracted from the biomass mixture. This made the resulting lignin, which is usually a light brown powder, an almost black powder. The same happened for high extraction temperatures of up to 200 °C, yielding around 95 %. As the lignin content for spruce sawdust was 22 ± 2 wt%, the purity could be calculated. The purity for lignin extracted with optimal pretreatment methods was around 93 %. It made no difference on the purity of whether ultrasonic pretreatment took place or not. An increase in extraction time to 24 h or greater and an increase in extraction temperature to 200 °C decreased the purity to around 45 %. Purity measurements were more important for determining the optimal extraction parameters, such as the composition of the GVL/water solvent mixture, the acid concentration, and the solid loading percentage. The results of this investigation are shown in the following paragraph.

To achieve these optimum yields, the parameters of the extraction process also had to be optimized. These consist of the composition of the GVL/water solvent mixture, the sulfuric acid concentration, and the solid loading percentage. For all three, extractions with variations of their values were performed. The resulting lignin was analyzed via yield and purity to be able to determine the optimum extraction parameters. For all extractions, the following default conditions were used: 120 °C as extraction temperature, 120 min as extraction time, GVL/water as solvent mixture, spruce sawdust as biomass source, and sulfuric acid as acid components. Figure 2 shows the results for the variation of the GVL/water compositions. Here, the sulfuric acid concentration of 0.1 mol/L and the solid loading of 10 wt% (weight percent) were used.

Figure 2: Variation of GVL/water wt%/wt% solvent mixture composition for lignin extraction. Other extraction conditions were 120 °C, 120 min, 10 wt% spruce sawdust, and 0.1 mol/L sulfuric acid. Yield (black) and purity (red) are depicted in a double-y-axis system, differently scaled.

The optimum GVL/water composition for the lignin extraction solvent mixture was 9/1 wt/wt. The purity of the lignin reached 99 %, while the yield was between 40 and 50 % for one extraction step. Increasing the GVL content towards 100 % would increase the yield, but at cost of the purity of the extracted lignin. If no water is present, swelling is reduced and decomposition of the polysaccharides is increased, leading to lower purity. If too much water is present, the solubility of lignin in the solvent mixture is decreased, as lignin is not water-soluble.

Figure 3 shows the results for the variation of sulfuric acid concentration. Here, the GVL/water composition of 9/1 wt/wt and a solid loading of 10 wt% were used.

Figure 1: Variation of the sulfuric acid concentration for lignin extraction. Other extraction conditions were 120 °C, 120 min, GVL/water composition of 9/1 wt/wt, and 10 wt% spruce sawdust. Yield (black) and purity (red) are depicted in a double-y-axis system, differently scaled.

Low sulfuric acid concentrations did not have the desired effect of efficiently cleaving lignin linkages to dissolve the lignin in the solvent mixture. While increasing the sulfuric acid concentration from 0.005 to 0.075 mol/L, the lignin yield increased with the purity staying consistent around 95 %. With a further increase in sulfuric acid concentration towards 0.5 mol/L, the yield still increased, but the purity decreased to around 75 %. After around 0.1 mol/L, purity started to decrease due to polysaccharide chains getting cleaved under highly acidic conditions. Additionally, condensed aromatic structures were forming from lignin oligomer condensation reactions. Large concentrations of sulfuric acid can also degrade lignin molecules, leading to lower purities. A sulfuric acid concentration of 0.075 mol/L was ideal for lignin extraction, providing high yields of around 50 % and high purities of around 95 %.

Figure 4 shows the results for the variation of the solid loading with spruce sawdust. Here, the GVL/water composition of 9/1 wt/wt and a sulfuric acid concentration of 0.075 mol/L were used.

With an in-

Figure 2: Variation of the solid loading weight percentage of spruce sawdust for lignin extraction. Other extraction conditions were 120 °C, 120 min, GVL/water composition of 9/1 wt/wt, and 0.075 mol/L sulfuric acid concentration. Yield (black) and purity (red) are depicted in a double-y-axis system, differently scaled.

creased solid loading weight percentage of spruce sawdust in lignin extractions, the lignin yields slightly decreased. This was due to less acid being active at each lignocellulose structure. Up to 12 w% solid loading was possible until the stirring of the mixture was impossible due to the lack of liquid substance. The purity stayed around 95 % for all extractions. The solid loading weight percentage depended more on the volume of the biomass source. For spruce sawdust, a solid loading weight percentage of 10 w% was chosen to be ideal, so a minimum amount of solvent is wasted. For biomass sources of different nut shells, the solid loading increased to 20 % due to the lower volume of the nutshell powder. For coffee silverskin or peanut skin, the optimum solid loading was 5 w%, as the volume of the skin pieces is higher and thus needed more solvent to achieve optimum stirring conditions. The optimum extraction parameters for the lignin extraction from spruce wood sawdust were determined: 120 °C, 120 min, GVL/water solvent composition of 9/1, sulfuric acid concentration of 0.075 mol/L, and solid loading of 10 w%. In general, the extraction methods for other used biomass sources were similar. Only the solid loading weight percentage was adjusted according to the volume of the biomass source. Other biomass sources thus resulted in similar lignin yields than from spruce sawdust of around 95 % after three extraction steps, with a purity around 90 %.

2. Aldehyde assisted extraction process optimization (AAF process)

The starting point for the optimization of the AAF¹⁰ process was the following research done before with the following conditions: The reaction flask was loaded with 2 g of spruce, 18 mL of GVL, 0.4 g of a 37 % hydrochloric acid solution, 1.26 g of distilled water, and 1.9 mL propionic aldehyde. The reaction conditions were 120 °C for 2 h. The mixture was filtered to remove the cellulose, neutralized, and precipitated in 10 parts distilled water. After conducting the first experiments, the resulting brown suspension was very stable. The produced lignin particles were small and well dispersed in a suspension, which was stable for weeks at RT. Filtration trials via different filtration methods always ended up in clogged filters. Therefore, the first optimization step was to implement a centrifugation step after precipitation to recover the lignin by subsequent filtration via the Buechner funnel using simple filter paper. The first lignins produced were of low quality; the residue was mostly black and had a gel-like texture. These presumably condensed lignins were disregarded, and the following extractions were carried out without water to eliminate another variable that could potentially promote the condensation of lignin.

To obtain less condensed lignins, extraction temperatures were varied. HSQC spectra of the isolated lignins were recorded, and their extraction yields (based on 2 g biomass) were weighted. The spectra show distinct signals that can be used to evaluate the quality of the extracted lignin. The β -O-4 bond protection signals PA₁, PA _{α} , and PA _{β} were chosen because these provided the most consistent results for the ether content calculation method. The protection rate of β -O-4 bonds was 100%. Other lignin bond types were not analyzed using this method. The method provided moderate accuracy but was sufficient to compare samples to each other.

Figure 5: Influence of extraction temperatures. HSQC spectra and yields of spruce lignins with different extraction temperatures. Conditions: 2 g spruce, 0.4 g HCl, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h. NMR solvent: DMSO-*d*₆.

Figure 5 illustrates the used protection signals and shows that the intensity of protection signals decreases with rising extraction temperatures. The spectra also show less distinguishable peaks for the G-units as the temperature is increased. The ether contents were 29 % for 90 °C and 25 % for 100 °C. Ether contents were not determinable for 110 °C and 120 °C as the protection group signals were too low. The 90 °C and 100 °C ether contents were a good starting point for further experiments. The yields in the figure suggest a yield growth with rising temperatures, even up to 727 mg in the case of 120 °C. To put the yields in perspective, the yields were calculated as a percentage of the theoretical maximum yield. The maximum mass yield was calculated based on biomass lignin content and the amount of mass increase due to the

acetalization process on the β -O-4 bonds. The corrected yields were 59 % (90 °C), 127 % (100 °C), 104 % (110 °C), and 156 % (120 °C). Yields above 100 % indicate that additional components besides lignin were extracted from the biomass. The additional mass could be due to protected C6 sugars from depolymerized cellulose, as the masses of other components in the biomass would not add up to these yields. Another observation was the darker lignin color for higher extraction temperatures. The 120 °C lignin appeared to be dark brown to almost black. In summary, extraction temperatures of 90 – 100 °C showed the best balance between retention of ether bonds and yield. The 100 °C extraction sample was used as a benchmark for further optimization of variables.

In comparison to the default extraction process, HCl was used instead of sulfuric acid. Sulfuric acid led to a less effective protection rate of < 90 %. The influence of different acid contents during the extraction was examined using the following experiment setup: The acid content of the 100 °C experiment was cut to half (0.2 g), and the reaction temperature was increased to 120 °C to account for an estimated lower extraction yield. The goal was to determine whether a lower acid content combined with a higher extraction temperature would yield a higher-quality lignin. The yield with lowered HCl concentration was 421 mg, which was still lower than the reference (592 mg). The reduced acid sample showed poor retention of ether bonds and a high degree of condensation (figure 6). To understand what happens during the condensation process, the molar mass distribution was analyzed by GPC. The GPC analysis revealed that at 100 °C, the lignin had an M_n of 1967 Da, an M_w of 4194 Da, and a polydispersity index \mathcal{D} of 2.13. This indicates that typical lignin oligomers are composed of 17 – 18 guacyl units (assuming 236 g/mol per monomeric unit). At 120 °C and with lowered acid concentration, the M_n decreased to 1068 Da, the M_w to 3011 Da, and the \mathcal{D} increased to 2.82, indicating greater fragmentation and a broader molecular weight distribution at higher temperatures. The typical oligomer consists of 12 to 13 guacyl units in this case, which is significantly shorter than the reference. This is counterintuitive as the molecular weight should increase due to the newly formed C-C-bonds, but the enhanced hydrolysis activity seems to clearly outweigh the molecular weight increase. Higher acid contents were not considered to prevent excessive hydrolysis of carbohydrates. The initial acid concentration was kept constant for the following experiments as the variation was not beneficial.

Figure 6: 2D HSQC spectrum of lignin extraction with lowered HCl content. Reaction conditions: 2 g spruce, 18 mL GVL, 0.2 g HCl 37%, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h, reaction temperature: 120 °C. NMR solvent: DMSO- d_6 .

Another interesting variable was the effect of additional water during the extraction. Additional water could increase the biomass swelling capacity of GVL and is an important factor for large-scale applications, as biomass might not be perfectly dried in all cases. The extraction was conducted similarly to the 100 °C experiment (2 g spruce, 18 mL of GVL, 0.4 g HCl 37 %, 1.26 g

of H₂O, 1.9 mL PA were, 100 °C, 3 h). The lignin was isolated as a light brown powder (396 mg, 85 %). This is clearly lower than the 127 % yield from the benchmark experiment. A resulting 18 % ether content was almost equal to the reference without additional water (25 %). The extracted lignin had a lighter color than the 100 °C reference but also had a slightly lower ether content and yield. Based on these findings, it can be said that water does not pose a problem during extractions but reduces the yield (figure 7).

The influence of the neutralization method was studied because the neutralization of black liquor could be avoided if deemed unnecessary. The extraction process until neutralization was

Figure 7: 2D HSQC spectrum of lignin extraction with additional water. Reaction conditions: 2 g spruce, 18 mL GVL, 0.4 g HCl 37%, 1.2 mL H₂O, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h, reaction temperature: 100 °C. NMR solvent: DMSO-*d*₆.

carried out identically to the benchmark experiment. Three neutralization variants were investigated. 1) Neutralization by adding 0.672 g NaHCO₃ and stirring for 30 min. (neutralization like in 100 °C benchmark) 2) Neutralization by addition of 0.672 g NaHCO₃ in 5 mL distilled water and stirring for 5 min. 3) Precipitation in water without neutralization. All samples were precipitated in 10 parts of water after their neutralization procedure. Lignin from the first sample was isolated as a medium brown powder (592 mg, 127 %). Lignin from the second sample, neutralized with NaHCO₃ in 5 mL water, was isolated as a brown powder with a similar color (598 mg, 128 %). Non-neutralized lignin was isolated as a black powder (427 mg, 92 %). **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.** shows the HSQC spectra of the NaHCO₃ (aq) neutralized

Figure 8: 2D HSQC spectra of lignins with different neutralization method. Left side: 0.672 g NaHCO₃ in 5 mL water. Right side: Without neutralization. Extraction conditions: 2 g spruce, 18 mL GVL, 0.4 g HCl 37%, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h, reaction temperature: 100 °C. NMR solvent: DMSO-*d*₆.

and the non-neutralized lignins. The lignin neutralized with NaHCO₃ in 5 mL water behaved similarly to the benchmark in terms of yield, color, and ether content (17 %). Ether content of

the sample without neutralization was not detectable as it showed a strongly condensed structure (figure 8). The series of experiments points out the need for neutralization. Adding NaHCO_3 solubilized in water did not affect the product outcome but has the disadvantage of adding additional complexity to the process as the solubilized salt must be removed later on. In the case of neutralization by solid salt, removal of the salt is easily achieved through filtration after neutralization. This advantage was decisive for the use of this neutralization method for following optimizations.

To enhance the sustainability of the process, the liquid-to-solid ratio was varied to reduce the use of GVL. The amount of GVL was reduced from 18 mL to 10 mL without changing any of the other variables. Lignin was isolated as a medium brown powder (639 mg, 137 %). The color was similar to the reference lignin. The ether content of the lignin was 17 %, and showed signs of condensation based on protection signal intensity and shape of G-units. The harsher extraction conditions due to the increased local acid concentration led to a higher yield and higher degree of condensation (figure 9). The lowered GVL content has proven to work similarly and also allowed for a lower amount of water to be needed for precipitation. Looking at the results of the liquid/solid load experiment, the reaction temperature was reduced to 85 °C to account for the higher acid concentration during extraction. The amount of biomass was increased to 5 g to ensure consistent stirring of the mixture in a 100 mL glass flask throughout the whole extraction. The other reagents were proportionally scaled up to the adjusted batch size: 5 g of spruce, 27.5 mL of GVL, 5.3 mL of propionaldehyde, and 0.94 mL of 37% HCl (aq). The optimized extractions produced medium brown lignin near theoretical yields (1.145 g, 99 %). The ether content of the lignin was 34 % and thus the highest ether content in the series of experiments. These extraction conditions were identified as the ideal lignin extraction conditions biomass fractionation process, allowing for a full removal of lignin and hemicellulose and a pure residual cellulose.

Figure 9: 2D HSQC spectrum of lignin extraction with increased solid to liquid ratio. Reaction conditions: 2 g spruce, 10 mL GVL, 0.4 g HCl 37%, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h, reaction temperature: 100 °C. NMR solvent: DMSO-d_6 .

After reducing the solvent use through optimization of the load ratio, further optimization regarding the sustainability of the process was possible in the step of precipitation and purification. The principle of precipitation of black liquor relies on the addition of an antisolvent to reduce the solubility of lignin in the precipitation solution. The solution can either be made as polar as possible or as non-polar as possible. Two approaches were tested to optimize the solvent consumption during the precipitation step. Firstly, a reduced quantity of water (5 parts instead of 10 parts per part black liquor) was used to precipitate the lignin. Secondly, a range of green non-polar solvents was screened to avoid the costly distillation process of water. Lastly, different purification methods for the isolated lignins were investigated.

The 5-part water precipitation experiment was still conducted based on the 100 °C benchmark experiment. The black liquor was neutralized and precipitated in 5 parts of water. After centrifugation, the precipitate formed as a gel-like residue, which was hard to handle. The gel residue was loaded in a tube filled with 10 mL of distilled water and placed into an ultrasonic bath for 10 min. The residue did not solidify enough to isolate the lignin, which was dried for 3 days using a desiccator. The lignin was isolated as a dark brown powder (517 mg, 111 %), slightly lower than the 127 % yield from the benchmark. Surprisingly, the isolated lignin showed strong indicators of condensation and very low intensity of protection group signals. The condensation might have occurred during the ultrasonic bath with water. This experiment showcases the sensitivity of the lignin during the precipitation and purification stages. Lower water contents can be used for successful precipitation, but more refined solidification methods are needed (figure 10).

Figure 10: 2D HSQC spectrum of lignin precipitated in 5 parts of water. Reaction conditions: 2 g spruce, 18 mL GVL, 0.4 g HCl 37%, 1.9 mL propionaldehyde, reaction time: 3 h, reaction temperature: 100 °C. NMR solvent: DMSO- d_6 .

Trials towards non-polar precipitation involved some adaptations of the fractionation process. The absence of water, and therefore the absence of a traceable pH value during the process, made it difficult to measure neutralization efficacy. Methanol was added to ensure the dissolution of NaHCO₃ and NaCl. Several fossil and bio-based non-polar solvents were tested as anti-solvents. The GVL-based black liquor did not mix with n-heptane, n-hexane, n-pentane, and cyclohexane. Further trials with limonene, diethyl ether, and cyclopentyl methyl ether led to low yields of < 40 %. Based on these findings, a new precipitation idea was considered: The black liquor should be evaporated and later redissolved in a solvent miscible with hydrocarbons. For this purpose, 27.5 mL black liquor (containing an initial 5 g load of spruce) was evaporated using a short-path vacuum distillation setup. The recovered GVL was analyzed by ¹H NMR and showed no signs of degradation. The residue was resolubilized in EtOAc and precipitated in n-heptane. The orange-colored solution containing the protected hemicellulose sugars was easily decanted, and the lignin easily precipitated. The gel-like lignin precipitate had to be solidified using 20 mL of water. This step was necessary to remove GVL traces in the lignin residue. The resulting lignin was isolated as a brown powder.

Both precipitation procedures showed different behavior during the purification step of the lignin. The reason for implementing a washing step became apparent after the yield collection from the non-polar precipitation route. The 52 % higher yield with identical extraction conditions was probably due to different precipitation behavior. It was assumed that protected sugars were retained in the lignin rather than being solubilized by the EtOAc/n-heptane solution. Several solvents were tried to extract the fraction of protected sugars from the isolated crude lignin. Firstly, the polar precipitated lignins were extracted by cyclopentyl methylether, limonene, cyclohexane, or diethyl ether. Cyclopentyl methylether extraction led to a mass loss of 58 % and a brownly colored washing solution due to the solubilization of protected lignin. Limonene led

to a 45 % mass loss because of difficulties during the in vacuo drying process. Cyclohexane led to a mass loss of 2 %, which is too low to extract notable amounts of protected sugars. Diethyl ether led to a 10 % mass loss and an orange-colored washing solution. A difference was noted during the washing step when using non-polar precipitated lignins. The color of the diethyl ether solution was a more intense orange compared to the polar precipitation route. This stresses the importance of the washing step for the non-polar precipitation route, as fewer sugars were retained in the initial precipitation solution. Figure 11 shows the NMR spectra of polar precipitated birch lignin before and after washing with Et₂O, along with the spectrum of non-polar precipitated lignin subjected to an Et₂O wash.

Figure 11: Lignin purification and comparison between precipitation methods. First two: 2D HSQC spectra of polar precipitated birch lignin before and after Et₂O wash. Last one: Non-polar precipitated Et₂O purified birch lignin. Conditions: 85 °C, 3 h (methods *Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.* & *Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.*). NMR solvent: DMSO-*d*₆.

Three relevant regions of the purified lignin spectra can be assigned. The alkyl region (¹H, δ: 0 – 3 ppm) demonstrates the successful removal of aliphatic degradation impurities in the alkyl region. The purified lignins also allow easy assignment of the propionaldehyde protons (PA1 & PA2). The oxygenated alkyl region (¹H, δ: 3 – 6 ppm) demonstrates the bonds in the lignin structure and the successful removal of protected sugars. The most prominent signals are those along beta-O-4 propyl structures (α, β, γ). The characteristic doublets of at 6.04 ppm and 6.00 ppm are not present in the purified spectrum. The aromatic region (¹H, δ: 6 – 9 ppm) is not affected by the purification. Another finding from spectra two and three is that the quality of lignins is identical, independent of their purification route. Overall, the purification process achieves a high lignin purity with low lignin loss.

3. NMR spectroscopy detailed method

Lignin and sugar molecules were analyzed in 2D-HSQC-NMR spectra using a method established by Zijlstra et al. (2019)¹¹. The content of each monomeric building block and the content of each linkage type can be calculated via integration of the respective signals. Lignin consists of the three main building blocks guaiacyl (G), syringyl (S), and p-hydroxyphenyl (H). Each of those show distinguishable signals in the HSQC spectrum. Similar to the monomeric units, each linkage type of lignin, mainly β-O-4', β-β', and β-5', also show distinguishable signals. Each building block and linkage unit has distinct labelling, referring to signal ranges in the HSQC spectrum (see table 1, figure 12).

Table 1: Signal ranges for different lignin subunit and linkage units. Labelling can be seen in figure 2.

Signal	Proton range [ppm]	Carbon range [ppm]
S(2,6)	6.48 - 6.90	104.0 - 109.0
S(con)	6.35 - 6.65	106.0 - 109.0
G(2)	6.78 - 7.14	111.5 - 116.0

G(5)	6.48 - 7.06	115.0 - 120.5
G(6)	6.65 - 6.96	120.5 - 124.5
H(2,6)	7.05 - 7.29	128.5 - 133.0
β -O-4' $_{\alpha}$	4.76 - 5.10	73.0 - 77.5
β -O-4' $_{\beta}$	4.03 - 4.48	85.0 - 90.5
β -O-4' $_{\gamma}$	3.10 - 4.00	58.5 - 62.0
β -5' $_{\alpha}$	5.42 - 5.63	88.0 - 92.0
β -5' $_{\beta}$	3.36 - 3.56	53.0 - 54.5
β -5' $_{\gamma}$	3.50 - 4.00	62.0 - 64.5
β - β' $_{\alpha}$	4.59 - 4.77	86.5 - 89.5
β - β' $_{\beta}$	2.98 - 3.20	55.5 - 59.0
β - β' $_{\gamma}$	3.75 - 3.96 / 4.10 - 4.31	72.5 - 76.0

Figure 12: Labeling of all atoms relevant for 2D-HSQC-NMR analysis and interpretation for all lignin subunit and linkage units. A = Labeling of protected lignin structures for protection rate analysis through 2D-HSQC-NMR.

Via equation (1), the total aromatic integral is calculated.

$$\text{total aromatic} = (S(2,6) + S(\text{con})) + \frac{G(2) + G(5) + G(6) - H(2,6)}{3} + \frac{H(2,6)}{2} \quad (1)$$

With the total aromatic integral, the percentages of the G, H, and S units can be calculated via equations (2), (3), and (4) respectively.

$$S \text{ content} = \frac{(S(2,6) + S(\text{con}))}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (2)$$

$$G \text{ content} = \frac{\left(\frac{G(2) + G(5) + G(6) - H(2,6)}{3}\right)}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (3)$$

$$H \text{ content} = \frac{\left(\frac{H(2,6)}{2}\right)}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (4)$$

Additionally, the number of linkages for every one hundred aromatic units can be calculated for each linkage type via equations (5), (6), and (7). Only the α -atoms of linkages are used for this calculation.

$$\beta - O - 4' \text{ content} = \frac{(\beta - O - 4'_{\alpha})}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (5)$$

$$\beta - 5' \text{ content} = \frac{(\beta - 5'_{\alpha})}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (6)$$

$$\beta - \beta' \text{ content} = \frac{(\beta - \beta'_{\alpha})}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (7)$$

A full compositional analysis of extracted lignin samples was possible with this method. Even acetal-protected lignin samples from hydrogenolysis could be analyzed. Since acetal-protected linkage signals have a different chemical environment, the signals distribute to different ppm ranges. This makes it possible to calculate the percentage of acetal-protected (A) linkages compared to all linkages present in lignin samples. Figure 1 also shows the labelling of acetal-protected linkage structures. The A_{α} signal was discovered at a [proton/carbon] range of [(4.0 – 4.2)/(74 – 79)]. Via equation (8), it is possible to calculate the number of acetal-protected linkages per one hundred aromatic units in extracted lignin. Equation (9) describes the calculation of percentage β -O-4' linkages that are acetal-protected.

$$A \text{ content} = \frac{A_{\alpha}}{\text{total aromatic}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (8)$$

$$\text{protected percentage} = \frac{A_{\alpha}}{(A_{\alpha} + \beta - O - 4'_{\alpha})} \cdot 100 \% \quad (9)$$

The monomeric sugar content in extracted degraded hemicellulose was determined through quantitative $^1\text{H-NMR}$ using maleic acid as internal standard. A certain amount of solvent-free depolymerized hemicellulose (approx. 10 mg) and a certain amount of maleic acid (approx. 5 mg) were solubilized in 1 mL DMSO- d_6 . The calculation was done according to equation (10).

$$P_{\text{Sugar}} = \frac{I_{\text{Sugar}}}{I_{\text{IS}}} * \frac{n_{\text{Protons, IS}}}{n_{\text{Protons, Sugar}}} * \frac{M_{\text{Sugar}}}{M_{\text{IS}}} * \frac{m_{\text{IS}}}{m_{\text{Sugar}}} * P_{\text{IS}} \quad (10)$$

Where P (%) was the purity of the substance, I was the peak integral, n was the number of protons in the signal, M (g/mol) was the molecular weight, and m (g) was the sample mass. The internal standard (IS) for quantification was maleic acid with a purity of 99 % and a molecular weight of 116.07 g/mol.

4. Solvent abbreviations

Table 2 shows the names, identifiers, and abbreviations for different organic solvents used for the introductory solvent screening for lignin solubilization.

Table 2: Abbreviations, identifiers and sources of σ -profiles of the compounds considered in the COSMO-SAC study.

Abbreviation	Name	CAS RN	σ -profile source ^a
ATEC	Acetyl triethyl citrate	77-89-4	this work
DBM	Maleic acid dibutyl ester	105-76-0	this work

DBS	Dibutyl sebacate	109-43-3	this work
DCAC	Diethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate	112-15-2	this work
DFX	Diformylxylose	n/a ^b	this work
DLG	Dihydrolevoglucosenone (Cyrene)	53716-82-8	this work
DMF	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	68-12-2	UD
DMI	Dimethyl isosorbide	5306-85-4	this work
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide	67-68-5	UD
EG	Ethylene glycol	107-21-1	UD
EtOAc	Ethyl acetate	141-78-6	UD
GVL	γ -Valerolactone	108-29-2	this work
NMP	<i>N</i> -Methyl-2-pyrrolidone	872-50-4	UD
PC	Propylene carbonate	108-32-7	UD
PCA	<i>p</i> -Coumaryl alcohol	20649-40-5	this work
TEC	Triethyl citrate	77-93-0	this work
TEP	Triethyl phosphate	78-40-0	this work
THF	Tetrahydrofuran	109-99-9	UD
Triacetin	Glycerol triacetate	102-76-1	this work
	1,4-Dioxane	123-91-1	UD
	Acetone	67-64-1	UD
	Acetonitrile	75-05-8	UD
	Benzene	71-43-2	UD
	<i>p</i> -Cymene	99-87-6	UD
	Water	7732-18-5	UD

^a The acronym UD relates to the University of Delaware database of σ -profiles, distributed together with the open source COSMO-SAC package¹².

^b No CAS RN has been assigned to DFX yet. SMILES:
O1CO[C@@H]2[C@@H](C1)O[C@H]1[C@H]2OCO1.

5. GVL/Water/Lignin ternary phase diagram

Figure 13 shows the ternary phase diagram of GVL/water/OSL, which was recorded by adding OSL to different GVL/water mixtures until no more dissolution occurred. The mixtures close to the phase boundary in the GVL-rich region became very dark and viscous with more OSL addition. The water-rich side showed low lignin solubility. Region 2 describes mixtures with colloidal lignin agglomerations in a GVL/water/dissolved OSL mixture. Region 1 describes homogenous one-phasic mixtures of GVK/water/OSL.

Figure 13: Ternary phase diagram of GVL/Water/OSL (Organosolv Lignin). Region 2: heterogenous region with lignin agglomerations. Region 1: homogenous region with dissolved lignin in GVL/water mixtures.

6. Quantification of structural changes in MD simulations

The structural changes in GVL/water/PCA mixtures that were observed with MD simulations were quantified in figure 14.

Figure 14: Proximal (i.e., closest distance) distribution of water and GVL around PCA (left), its polar hydroxyl parts (middle), and non-polar hydrocarbon domain (right). The proximal volume shells (3, 4, 5 Å) and decomposition of PCA molecule into functional groups (hydroxyls in red, hydrocarbons in gray) are shown in the inset. The arrows denote the significant strengthening of hydroxyl hydration (black) and mild increase of solvation of hydrocarbon domain by GVL (blue), which overall improves the solubility of PCA in GVL/water mixture when compared to either of the pure solvents.

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